

AN EXAMINATION OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL SPORTSPERSONSHIP ORIENTATION LEVELS OF PROFESSIONAL ATHLETES

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Abstract:

This study aims to obtain general information about the sportspersonship levels of athletes who compete professionally in volleyball, football, and basketball leagues. The study sample consists of 148 professional athletes competing in one 1st league basketball team (n: 15), two 2nd league volleyball teams (n: 48), and one 2nd league and two 3rd league football teams (n: 85). These are teams from Gaziantep, Adana, and Hatay provinces, in Turkey. The Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientations Scale (MSOS-25) used in this study contains 25 items (5 items per subscale) and is being assessed on a 5-point scale. The original MSOS-25's subscales include; Respect for social conventions (paraphrased as *Compliance with social norms*), Respect for the rules and the officials (paraphrased as *Respect for rules and management*), Respect for one's full commitment toward sport participation (paraphrased as *Commitment to responsibilities in sports*), and Respect and concern for the opponent (paraphrased as *Respect for the opponent*) (Balçıkanlı, 2010). Kruskal Wallis H was used to compare the subscales' data to age groups, branches, experience, and leagues. As the data of the MSOS's subscales are not normally distributed, the Mann Whitney U test was used to compare the subscales data to the gender and education level. The results showed significant differences between sportspersonship indices and, age, educational level, and league variables. However, there was no significant difference in terms of gender, branch, and experience.

Keywords: sportspersonship, athletes, basketball, volleyball

1. Introduction

There are many studies on the concept of sportspersonship in Turkey and the world. Issues such as compliance with social norms, obeying rules, respecting management, respecting the opponent, fair-play, taking responsibility, and duty awareness are very

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important in sports life, as they are in the daily life of individuals. When the concept of sportspersonship is considered as a part of our social life, it expresses the important concepts that exist within the sport, especially respect and obeying the rules. In the process from the primitive ages to the present day, obeying rules and respect have always been important in society, especially due to the need for people to live and act together. In the concept of sport, which is a part of social life, sportspersonship (respecting yourself, respecting the opponent, and following the rules) is one of the basic elements. According to this, sportspersonship is the physical, mental, and social development of a person who does sports as an amateur or a professional and follows the prescribed rules. In other words, it is a system of individual and social values oriented to the action that makes play and sports activity possible (Şahin et al., 2015).

The concept of sportspersonship has emerged as an expression of respect for human dignity in the first place, and it has established itself as a moral principle that causes fair and honest play in every stage and every kind of sport (Pehlivan, 2004). Sportspersonship, which stands out in the concept of sports and is accepted as a moral concept and education principle, contains human characteristics such as obeying the rules of the game, respect for others, rights, justice, and gentleness; It rejects behaviors that are not accepted by the society such as fraud, lies, and non-compliance with the rules (Yapan, 2007). Two of the 8 principles that the International Sports Federations (IFs) emphasize to improve sportspersonship are "avoid violence in your game" and "control your anger". Another emphasized principle "Be healthy and open-minded for a healthy body" expresses assertiveness (Keating, 2007). Some studies show that the level of sportspersonship of non-contact athletes is higher than those of contact sports (Esentürk et al., 2015; Tsai & Fung, 2005). Studies also show that those who do individual sports are significantly more aggressive than those who do team sports (Güner, 2006; Koruç & Bayar, 1990). Basketball is a widespread sport that is followed by a great majority of the world and can be found in almost every society and age group. The game is played at high tempo and jump, sudden running, sudden change of direction between the movement model, as the continuous and sudden changes occur in the majority of the game takes place in anaerobic (oxygen-free metabolism) environment (Hoffman & Maresh, 2000; Crisafulli et al, 2002). It's important for the athletes to maintain their skill at the highest level for 40 minutes on a 28-to-15m court with movements that require sudden acceleration and deceleration (such as shifts, side shifts, jumps, rebounds, and blocks). It is very important that an anaerobic endurance, quickness, and agility are at the highest level (Delextrat & Cohen, 2009). Because the ability to act quickly and make decisions in basketball is instant, the athlete must be ready and mobile for movements such as taking and dribbling, shooting, dribbling and rebounding at any time (Muratlı, Toraman & Çetin, 2000). The psychological characteristics that elite athletes should have are: appropriate personality traits depending on the sport branch, having a controllable internal focus of success and failure, high self-confidence and belief in the final success, intrinsic motivation, strong dominance of target orientation for sporting success, the ability present full concentration on the task, the ability to control emotion and arousal, the ability to cope

with the difficulties encountered, the ability to set up difficult goals and formulate plans to achieve them, the ability to self-motivate, the ability to use psychological methods such as imagination and self-control, and mental endurance (Cox, 2012). This study aims to examine the multidimensional sportspersonship orientation levels of professional athletes in light of this information.

2. Method

2.1 Study Group

The study sample consists of 148 professional athletes competing in one 1st league basketball team (n: 15), two 2nd league volleyball teams (n: 48), and one 2nd league and two 3rd league football teams (n: 85); these are teams from Gaziantep, Adana, and Hatay provinces, in Turkey. A total of 148 professional athletes who participated in the study were selected randomly from 6 teams that competed in the first half of the 2017-2018 season. Foreign athletes were not included in the study group, considering the possible cultural differences that may affect the findings of the study.

2.2 Data Collection Tool

The MSOS-25, developed by Vallerand et al. (1994) to determine the sportspersonship orientations of professional footballers, was used as the data collection tool (14, 23, 10, 24). The researcher adapted the scale to Turkish by using the back-translation technique. The scale was applied to 300 students who were randomly selected from Gazi University School of Physical Education and Sports, to test the intercultural differences and comprehensibility of the items. According to the results of the statistical analyzes, the items that were not understood were revised and corrected and the scale was reapplied to the same group. After the translation and pilot study phase, the validity and reliability study of the scale was conducted on 110 football players randomly selected from various football clubs in Ankara. The Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientations Scale (MSOS-25) used in this study contains 25 items (5 items per subscale) and is being assessed on a 5-point scale. The original MSOS-25's subscales include; Respect for social conventions (paraphrased as *Compliance with social norms*), Respect for the rules and the officials (paraphrased as *Respect for rules and management*), Respect for one's full commitment toward sport participation (paraphrased as *Commitment to responsibilities in sports*), Respect and concern for the opponent (paraphrased as *Respect for the opponent*), and Negative approach toward the practice of sport. As a result of the initial factor-analysis of the 25 items in the MSOS, 5 items (items 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25) in the Negative Approach Toward the Practice of Sport subscale didn't work. This subscale was not added to the study in the second factor-analysis. The Turkish version of the Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Scale has a 4-factor structure and 20 items. Cronbach Alpha values are as follows; Factor 1 (Compliance with Social Norms) is 0.86, Factor 2 (Respect for Rules and Management) is 0.83, Factor 3 (Commitment to Responsibilities in Sports) is 0.91, and Factor 4 (Respect for the Opponent) is 0.82. Values are highly reliable. According to

these results, it can be said that the Turkish version of the Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Scale has a valid and reliable structure.

2.3 Statistical Analyses

The obtained data was analyzed using SPSS 22. Kruskal Wallis H was used to compare the subscales' data to age groups, branches, experience, and leagues. As the data of the MSOS's subscales are not normally distributed, the Mann Whitney U test was used to compare the subscales data to the gender and education level.

The results showed significant differences between sportspersonship indices and, age, educational level, and league variables. However, there was no significant difference in terms of gender, branch, and experience. Spearman Correlation analysis was used to examine the relationship between scale scores. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

3. Findings

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Participants' Demographic Information

Variables	Sub-variables	f	%
Age Group	16-19 y/o	17	
	20-23 y/o	52	
	24-27 y/o	45	
	27+ y/o	34	
Gender	Male	117	
	Female	31	
Branch	Volleyball	48	
	Football	85	
	Basketball	15	
Education Level	University	51	
	High School	97	
Experience	1-5 years	16	
	6-10 years	50	
	11-15 years	54	
	15+ years	28	
League	1 st League	15	
	2 nd League	91	
	3 rd League	42	

Table 1 shows the variables, sub-variables, and descriptive statistics of the participants' demographic information. According to data the highest participation was from 20-23-year-olds in the Age variable, males in the Gender variable, football players in the Branch variable, high school graduates in the Education Level variable, and 6-15 years in the Experience variable.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Participants' Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Subscale Scores

Subscales	N	X	Ss
Compliance with social norms	141	4.20	0.635
Respect for rules and management	141	4.16	0.536
Commitment to responsibilities in sports	141	4.52	0.447
Respect for the opponent	141	3.89	0.659

Table 2 shows that participants have high levels of compliance with social norms and commitment to responsibility in sports, while respect for rules and management and respect for the opponent is above average.

Table 3: Comparison of Participants' Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Subscale Scores by Age Groups

Subscales	Ager Group	N	X	Ss	Mean Rank	x ²	p
Compliance with social norms	16-19 y/o	17	4.54	0.419	76.92	13.418	0.002
	20-23 y/o	52	4.08	0.646	50.51		
	24-27 y/o	45	4.03	0.708	48.94		
	27+ y/o	34	4.48	0.429	76.92		
Respect for rules and management	16-19 y/o	17	4.40	0.383	71.73	6.031	0.112
	20-23 y/o	52	4.08	0.571	51.56		
	24-27 y/o	45	4.10	0.542	53.39		
	27+ y/o	34	4.28	0.507	66.10		
Commitment to responsibilities in sports	16-19 y/o	17	4.75	0.203	74.50	5.671	0.233
	20-23 y/o	52	4.43	0.487	50.63		
	24-27 y/o	45	4.49	0.507	56.83		
	27+ y/o	34	4.60	0.323	61.02		
Respect for the opponent	16-19 y/o	17	4.12	0.592	69.00	2.479	0.245
	20-23 y/o	52	3.84	0.661	53.45		
	24-27 y/o	45	3.85	0.695	56.00		
	27+ y/o	34	3.93	0.648	60.44		

Table 3 shows that the participants' level of respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibilities in sports and respect for their opponents do not statistically differ according to age groups significantly ($p > 0.05$), while social norm compliance levels statistically differ according to age groups significantly ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4: Comparison of Participants' Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Subscale Scores by Gender

Subscales	Gender	N	X	Ss	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U	p
Compliance with social norms	Male	117	4.18	0.659	56.80	5850.5	494.5	0.387
	Female	31	4.40	0.268	64.05	704.5		
Respect for rules and management	Male	117	4.15	0.554	56.82	5852.0	496.0	0.376
	Female	31	4.33	0.300	63.91	703.0		
Commitment to responsibilities in sports	Male	117	4.51	0.460	57.30	5901.5	545.5	0.577
	Female	31	4.60	0.310	59.41	653.5		

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Respect for the opponent	Male	117	3.87	0.661	56.49	5818.0	462.0	0.123
	Female	31	4.11	0.628	67.00	737.0		

Table 4 shows that the participants' compliance with social norms, respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibilities in sports, and respect for their opponents do not statistically differ according to gender significantly ($p>0.05$).

Table 5: Comparison of Participants' Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Subscale Scores by Branches

Subscales	Branch	N	X	Ss	Mean Rank	χ^2	p
Compliance with social norms	Volleyball	48	4.27	0.546	59.05	0.543	0.682
	Football	85	4.17	0.673	56.53		
	Basketball	15	4.40	0.268	64.05		
Respect for rules and management	Volleyball	48	4.11	0.441	52.32	0.699	0.501
	Football	85	4.15	0.568	57.35		
	Basketball	15	4.33	0.300	63.91		
Commitment to responsibilities in sports	Volleyball	48	4.45	0.482	53.05	0.252	0.771
	Football	85	4.52	0.459	57.80		
	Basketball	15	4.60	0.310	59.41		
Respect for the opponent	Volleyball	48	3.69	0.666	48.27	1.785	0.311
	Football	85	3.89	0.661	57.47		
	Basketball	15	4.11	0.628	67.00		

Table 5 shows that the participants' compliance with social norms, respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibilities in sports and respect for their opponents do not statistically differ according to branch significantly ($p>0.05$).

Table 6: Comparison of Participants' Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Subscale Scores by Education Levels

Subscales	Education Level	N	X	Ss	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U	p
Compliance with social norms	University	51	4.16	0.581	53.09	1964.5	1261.5	0.422
	High School	97	4.22	0.661	59.62	4590.5		
Respect for rules and management	University	51	4.07	0.481	50.55	1870.5	1167.5	0.11
	High School	97	4.28	0.558	60.84	4684.5		
Commitment to responsibilities in sports	University	51	4.46	0.464	52.09	1927.5	1224.5	0.231
	High School	97	4.55	0.439	60.10	4627.5		
Respect for the opponent	University	51	3.85	0.724	56.14	2077.0	1374.0	0.548
	High School	97	3.91	0.630	58.16	4478.0		

Table 6 shows that according to the educational level of the participants, compliance with social norms, respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibility in sports and respect for their opponents do not statistically differ significantly ($p>0.05$).

Table 7: Comparison of Participants' Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Subscale Scores by Experience

Subscales	Experience	N	X	Ss	Mean Rank	χ^2	p
Compliance with social norms	1-5 years	16	4.53	0.462	75.17	1.383	0.510
	6-10 years	50	4.20	0.602	56.67		
	11-15 years	54	4.20	0.693	58.88		
	15+ years	28	4.14	0.597	52.34		
Respect for rules and management	1-5 years	16	4.07	0.643	48.83	3.852	0.377
	6-10 years	50	4.18	0.525	58.26		
	11-15 years	54	4.09	0.582	52.95		
	15+ years	28	4.38	0.364	70.88		
Commitment to responsibilities in sports	1-5 years	16	4.73	0.306	72.83	1.585	0.555
	6-10 years	50	4.54	0.469	59.84		
	11-15 years	54	4.48	0.460	53.80		
	15+ years	28	4.56	0.374	59.25		
Respect for the opponent	1-5 years	16	4.07	0.231	65.33	0.186	0.687
	6-10 years	50	3.90	0.714	57.36		
	11-15 years	54	3.89	0.651	57.48		
	15+ years	28	3.88	0.615	56.50		

Table 7 shows that the participants' compliance with social norms, respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibilities in sports, and respect for their opponents do not statistically differ according to experience significantly ($p>0.05$).

Table 8: Comparison of Participants' Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Subscale Scores by Leagues

Subscales	League	N	X	Ss	Mean Rank	χ^2	p
Compliance with social norms	1 st League	15	4.40	0.268	64.05	8.692	0.010
	2 nd League	91	3.96	0.738	45.87		
	3 rd League	42	4.34	0.550	64.63		
Respect for rules and management	1 st League	15	4.33	0.300	63.91	0.676	0.523
	2 nd League	91	4.14	0.651	58.56		
	3 rd League	42	4.15	0.478	55.57		
Commitment to responsibilities in sports	1 st League	15	4.60	0.310	59.41	1.839	0.422
	2 nd League	91	4.57	0.455	62.37		
	3 rd League	42	4.47	0.463	53.66		
Respect for the opponent	1 st League	15	4.11	0.628	67.00	2.746	0.123
	2 nd League	91	3.75	0.737	51.45		
	3 rd League	42	3.96	0.594	60.09		

Table 8 shows that the participants' level of respect for rules and management, commitment to sports responsibilities and respect for their opponents do not statistically differ according to the leagues significantly ($p>0.05$), while the levels of compliance with social norms statistically differ according to the leagues significantly ($p<0.05$). The level of compliance with social norms of the participants competing in 3rd League is significantly higher than those competing in 2nd League at a $p<0.05$ level.

Table 9: Correlations between Participants' Multidimensional Sports Orientation Subscale Scores

		Compliance with social norms	Respect for rules and management	Commitment to responsibilities in sports
Respect for rules and management	r	0.340**	-	
	p	0.000		
Commitment to responsibilities in sports	r	0.130**	0.210	-
	p	0.168	0.025	
Respect for the opponent	r	0.570**	0.367**	0.174
	p	0.000	0.000	0.064

Table 9 shows that there is a positive, statistically significant, and intermediate correlation between participants' compliance with social norms and respect for rules and management ($p < 0.01$); there is a positive, statistically significant, and intermediate correlation between compliance with social norms and respect for the opponent ($p < 0.01$); there is positive, statistically significant and below-intermediate correlations between compliance with social norms and commitment to responsibilities in sport ($p < 0.01$); there are positive, statistically significant and below-intermediate correlations between the level of respect for rules and management, and the level of commitment to responsibilities in sport, there is positive, statistically significant and intermediate correlations between the level of respect for rules and management, and respect for the opponent ($p < 0.01$).

4. Discussion and Result

This study on the multidimensional sportspersonship orientation levels of professional athletes shows that participants' levels of compliance with social norms, and commitment to responsibilities in sports are high, and their levels of respect for rules and management and respect for the opponent are above intermediate (Table 2). Chantal et al. (2005) found an important relationship between sportspersonship and aggression study. They observed no statistically significant difference for participants' respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibilities, and respect for the opponent, yet they observed a statistically significant difference between age groups for compliance with social norms ($p < 0.05$). The level of compliance with the social norms of the participants in the 16-19 and 27+ age groups is statistically significantly higher than those in the 20-23 and 24-27 age groups (Table 3). Compliance with social norms according to gender, respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibilities in sports and respect for the opponent do not statistically differ significantly (Table 4). Esentürk et al. (2015) found that women's sportspersonship levels were significantly higher than men's. Shields et al. (2007) didn't find a statistically significant difference between the sportspersonship behaviors of female and male students studying in the 5th, and 8th-grades. The participants' compliance with social norms, respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibilities in sports, and respect for the opponent do not differ statistically according to their branches (Table 5). The participants'

compliance with social norms, respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibilities in sports, and respect for the opponent do not differ statistically according to educational levels (Table 6). In a study, researchers examined high school students' sportspersonship behaviors according to some variables, and they found that sportspersonship behaviors related to physical education classes differed according to the gender of the students, and the type of sports interested them. Furthermore, they found a statistically significant negative correlation between sportspersonship behaviors and aggression values of the students in physical education classes (Koç & Güllü, 2016).

The participants' compliance with social norms, respect for rules and management, commitment to responsibilities in sports, and respect for the opponent do not differ statistically according to their age (Table 7). Researches found in their study that, students participating in volleyball competitions, which are a non-contact sport, showed higher sportspersonship values than those participating in basketball competitions (Tsai & Fung, 2005). According to leagues, the participants' levels of respect for rules and management, commitment level to sports responsibilities, and respect for the opponent do not differ statistically ($p>0.05$), yet their compliance with social norms differ significantly ($p<0.05$). The level of compliance with the social norms of the participants in the 3rd league is statistically higher than the participants in the 2nd league (Table 8). There is a positive, statistically significant, and below-intermediate correlation between participants' compliance with social norms and respect for rules and management at $p<0.05$ level; there is a positive, statistically significant, and intermediate correlation between compliance with social norms and respect for the opponent at $p<0.05$ level; there are positive, statistically significant and below-intermediate correlations between the level of respect for rules and management, and the level of commitment to responsibilities in sport, and between the level of respect for rules and management, and respect for the opponent at $p<0.05$ level (Table 9). Researchers found that participation in sports in secondary education institutions have a positive effect on the moral development of a child (Akandere, Baştuğ & Güler, 2009). As a result, this study shows that athletes' multidimensional sportspersonship indices statistically significantly differ according to the athletes' age, educational status, and leagues, yet there is no statistically significant difference according to gender, branch, and experience.

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